

K/100 g, and 1.2 ppm available Zn. The FYM contained 1.8% N and 0.45 ppm total P. FYM, all P and K, and 35 kg N/ha were applied basally; the remaining N was topdressed at panicle initiation. Grain yield was computed at 14% moisture.

No significant pest or disease damage or water stress occurred during crop development. All fertilizer treatments increased yield significantly (see table). Mean yield from plots given FYM alone was 20% higher than check plots. Supplementing FYM with extra N had no effect. FYM plus P significantly increased yield 18% over FYM alone. Yields with FYM supplemented with

N+P and from plots fertilized with N+P or N+P+K only did not differ significantly from yields with FYM+P.

The results indicate that utilization of nitrogen in FYM may be seriously limited by inadequate soil P. In Wangdiphodrang-Punakha, soil analyses now show that available P levels are generally low (less than 10 ppm). Available K and other plant nutrients appear to be adequate. These preliminary results suggest that in a region where use of inorganic fertilizer is very low but use of FYM is routine, more benefit could be obtained from supplementing FYM with P. □

Effect of FYM supplemented with N and P on yield of IR36. CARD, Wangdiphodrang, Bhutan, 1986.

FYM ^b (t/ha)	Fertilizer treatment ^a			Grain yield ^c (t/ha)
	N (kg/ha)	P (kg/ha)	K (kg/ha)	
0	0	0	0	4.8 c
7.5	0	0	0	5.8 b
7.5	35	0	0	5.3 bc
7.5	0	50	0	6.9 a
7.5	35	50	0	7.0 a
0	75	50	0	6.6 a
0	75	50	40	6.9 a
	CV (%)			4.5

^a N as urea, P as single superphosphate, K as muriate of potash. ^b Fresh weight. ^c Mean separation in a column by DMRT at the 5% level.

Phosphorus requirements in a rice - wheat cropping system

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We studied P requirements of rice grown in sequence with wheat in the field 1983 to 1987. Different combinations of P level (0, 13, and 26 kg P/ha) and P application (applying P to rice alone, wheat alone, or both rice and wheat) were laid out in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

At the beginning of the experiment in 1983, the soil (sandy loam, Typic Ustochrept) had pH 8.1, 0.29% organic C, and 14.5 kg Olsen's P/ha. All plots received 120 kg N and 23 kg K/ha. All

Influence of P on rice yield in a rice - wheat cropping system. Punjab, India, 1983-87.

P (kg/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)					
Rice	Wheat	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	Mean 1984-87
0	0	7.4	5.7	6.2	6.4	5.6	6.0
13	0	7.3	6.8	7.2	8.4	8.4	7.7
26	0	7.5	6.9	7.2	8.4	8.6	7.8
0	13	7.5	6.0	6.5	7.2	6.8	6.6
0	26	6.8	6.0	6.5	7.3	7.6	6.8
13	13	7.1	6.7	7.4	8.3	8.5	7.7
13	26	7.5	6.8	7.2	8.4	8.6	7.8
26	13	7.0	6.8	7.1	8.3	8.5	7.7
26	26	7.5	6.6	7.1	7.9	7.4	7.2
LSD (0.05)		ns	0.7	0.4	0.9	0.7	0.7

P and K and 1/3 N were applied before transplanting. The remaining N was applied at 21 d and 42 d after transplanting.

Rice responded significantly to direct application of up to 13 kg P/ha (see

table). Rice grown on the residue of 25 kg P/ha applied to the preceding wheat showed no response. Increasing P to 26 kg/ha for both rice and wheat slightly depressed rice yield. □

Effect of two phosphorus sources with or without azolla incorporation on rice yield in the Senegal River valley

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We compared a soluble-type P (triple superphosphate with 45% P₂O₅) and a natural type P (aluminum phosphate

Soil analysis. Fanaye P4 (Paleustollic Torrerts), Fanaye Station, Senegal.

pH		Texture ^a	Clay (%)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Organic matter ^b (%)	CEC ^c (meq/100 g)	Available P BRAY II (ppm)	Total P ^d (ppm)	Adsorbed P ^e at 0.2 ppm P in the soil solution (µg P/g of soil)
Soil:water (1:1)	KCl 1 N									
6.2	4.4	Clay	46.5	29.9	23.6	0.35	31.26	1.50	240	330

^a Bouyoucos method. ^b Walkley - Black method. ^c Cobaltihexamine method (Orsini et Remy 1976). ^d Perchloric acid digestion. ^e Fox and Kamprath method (1970).

with 34% P₂O₅). We also evaluated the influence of azolla incorporation on assimilation of P by rice.

The trial for four consecutive cropping seasons was conducted on a fine clayey soil Paleustollic Torrerts (see

table). The design was a randomized complete block with three replications. Treatments were no N or P, no N plus either of the 2 sources of P at the rate of 52 kg P/ha, 120 kg N (urea) plus either of the 2 sources of P at 52 kg P/ha, and 60 kg N (urea) + 60 kg N (azolla)/ha and O or 52 kg P, applied either split or all at once. Two crops of *Azolla pinnata* var. *imbricata*, of Indian origin (20 t/ha each, equivalent to 30 kg N/ha) were grown successively and incorporated before rice transplanting. The rice variety was Sri Malaysia.

After the third cropping season, rice yield showed no influence from P. After the fourth cropping season, during the 1985 rainy season, no significant difference in yield between the two P sources had occurred (see figure). However, although N and P levels were equivalent with triple superphosphate, yields were higher when azolla was incorporated. Uptake of P from a split application and assimilated by azolla seems better. The response of rice was

Effects of 2 P sources, applied with and without azolla incorporation, on grain yield of rice variety Sri Malaysia. Fanaye Research Station, Senegal River valley, 1985 rainy season. Basal application of P, except in treatment 6, where P was split-applied.

more pronounced with aluminum phosphate; the split application produced 0.9 t/ha more. By the end of

the fourth cropping season, the lack of P had caused an important yield reduction (2.0 and 3.0 t/ha). □

Disease management

Four fungicides for control of grain infection caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae*

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Grain discoloration caused by

Helminthosporium oryzae Breda de Haan, the causal agent of brown spot (BS), is a major problem in the 35,000 ha irrigated Rio Formoso rice project. A disease outbreak in Feb 1983, during the vegetative phase of the fourth successive planting of lowland rice variety IAC899 in CNPAF experimental fields indicated the possible role of infected plant debris. Despite 3 sprayings with maneb fungicide at 10-d intervals to control leaf infection, the disease retarded plant growth.

We evaluated four marketed spray fungicides for grain infection control in the same fields. The experiment used 8 m² direct seeded plots in a randomized block design with 8 replications. Fungicides were sprayed at recommended doses 3 times at 7-d intervals, beginning at 50% heading (92 d after seeding). Untreated controls were not maintained because in similar experiments, sprayed plots adjacent to untreated plots exhibited abnormally high disease intensities.

Effect of fungicide spray on BS control.^a Goiania, Goias, Brazil, 1983.

Fungicide	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Flag leaf lesions (no./leaf)		Diseased grains/panicle (%)		Unfilled grains/panicle ^b (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
		112 DAS	119 DAS	108 DAS	115 DAS		
Ziram 50% EC	1.5	8.91 a	27.47 a	27.76 a	44.58 ab	41.75 a	2.05 a
Thiophanate-methyl (20%) + chlorothalonil 50% WP	1.4	7.43 b	22.19 b	26.56 ab	45.64 a	41.16 a	2.03 a
Maneb 80% WP	1.6	8.59 ab	23.26 ab	25.71 ab	39.52 b	38.70 a	2.22 a
Captafol 48% EC	0.96	9.14 a	25.91 ab	23.30 b	39.34 b	34.83 a	2.41 a
CV (%)		12.0	13.5	11.8	10.2	17.2	15.2

^a Means of 8 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by Tukey test at the 5% level. DAS = days after seeding. ^b Unfilled grain percentage was based on 10 panicles/plot.